

FAIRGamma

Contribution for the FAIRisation of Gammapy

Summary

Gammapy aims to analyse Very-High-Energy gamma-ray data and to be used for multi-wavelength and multi-messenger data analysis. It is mature library already used for many scientific publications.

**But, our products lack proper FAIR information.
One must respect the FAIR4RS principles.**

Challenge

All Gammapy products must contain **metadata** and **Provenance information**, such that they are directly publishable with only minor data curation.

Metadata reduction scheme should be created, as well as Provenance format.

Results

- Addition of the context and fixity metadata (PR 4837, 4993, 5076, 5081, 5457, 5875)
- About to finalize the separation of the internal data model and the one of the input data
- Creation of internal metadata classes
- Design of the concept of “metadata reduction”
- Metadata format under finalization for the `Datasets`, including some minimal Provenance information
- Finalised new features are available in Gammapy v2.0.1 (The next release, v2.1, planned for end of March)

Sustainability

- All new features available in the next Gammapy releases
 - Zenodo, Software Heritage, Conda-Forge, PyPI, soon Docker images
- All new features fully documented in the official Gammapy documentation
 - One documentation per release
- Organization of annual schools

Solution

Within Gammapy :

- Roadmap about the Gammapy FAIRisation
- Design of a scheme for metadata handling

In open data-formatting projects :

- Implication into the CTAO Data Modeling group
- Leading the H.E.S.S. Archive group and the VODF project (Very-high-energy Open Data Format)

Exploitation of results

Sustainability

- Design with format-specific serialiser registry to allow easy addition of new formats
- Unitary testing and validation to guarantee long term support
- Constant training of new developers allowing a long-term maintainability

Exploitation

- Users able to search and access data stored into the Virtual Observatory
- Gammapy products generated by physicists will be (FA)IR permitting a direct publication with only minor data curation
- Publishable Gammapy products will contain Provenance: high reusability and trustability of the astrophysical products

